

CRISTAL

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

[D 1.3 Roadmaps as Blueprints for Wider Applicability and Use]

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission System
AGN	Agreement on Main Inland Waterways of International importance
Aipo	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
CEP	Courier Express Parcel
EPRS	Directorate-General for European Parliamentary Research Service
EU	European Union
FOS	Fiber Optic Sensors
GA	Grant Agreement
IBS	Intelligent Buoys System
IV	Infrastrutture Venete S.r. l
IWT	Inland waterway transport
KET	Key enabling technologies
KPI	Key performance indicator
LNG	Liquid Natural Gas
ML	Machine Learning
NST	Standard goods classification for transport statistics
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
SB	Smart Buoys
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data acquisition
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring

SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar
STOA	Scientific Foresight Unit
tkm	Tonne-kilometres
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
VCC	Value Creation Circle
VNF	Voies navigables de France

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1. Executive Summary

The main goal of this deliverable is to provide roadmaps based on the pilot sites. To report the work accomplished for the KPIs in WP1 it also contains a chapter about the selection of KPIs.

There is no requirement to merge the different roadmaps into one concluding plan how to implement new technologies or new processes into the IWT sector. Measures are individually reasoned by the conditions at the pilot sites, which may be comparable to many other IWT infrastructure, however, they remain individual. It however became obvious in the data collection, that the attempt to align these roadmaps at least into one common format is advisable to show the different approaches under one common theme.

The overall objectives of the CRISTAL project are of holistic nature. They support the system inland waterway transport rather than single goals in that sector. To strengthen the overall system, the pilot sites contribute with specific measures tested in a real operational environment or in laboratory conditions. By prioritizing the development of an effective IWT system, the focus is a continuous improvement and refinement of the processes and technologies that support the attainment of the desired outcome. This approach emphasizes the importance of consistently and intentionally investing in systems that foster success and sustainable growth.

For example, rather than setting just a goal of measuring sedimentation in rivers, the approach focuses on developing routines and processes around that obtained data that will lead to a better navigation forecast and other applications almost as a by-product as an improved system. The focus of CRISTAL is on creating a sustainable inland waterway transport system rather than just achieving a short-term goal or a single technology development.

The roadmaps illustrate in a great variety which strategies and tactics are applied to overcome the identified shortcomings in the overall IWT ecosystem. In CRISTAL, the system IWT receives a stimulation for an improvement for the infrastructure owners/ authorities in the form of

- Better maintenance routines and more insights into the status of concrete walls and lock gates
- Locating abandoned buoys
- Feasibility of cold ironing facilities

For the (potential users) of the IW infrastructure in the form of

- Electronic handling of freight documents
- Improved insights re. free berth facilities in ports and at locks
- More reliable and more detailed navigation forecasts
- New IWT supply chain models

If all pilot sites will fully succeed in applying new technologies and new processes cannot be assessed at this early stage of the project. The roadmaps are meant to support the pilots but also WP6 to further harmonise the approaches within the pilot sites at least to some extent. The KPIs have been developed and selected to be able to validate the performance and results of the pilot within task 10.3. The project

decided to provide a list to the pilots from which they chose the most suitable ones. It was also possible to add individual KPIs for the pilots.

1.1. Introduction

The roadmaps will outline the processes that will be carried out in the pilot test sites. The test sites have chosen different measures and technologies to contribute to the achievement of the project’s goals. The infrastructure authorities may change inspection routines for infrastructure and test new technologies for that purpose or deploy technologies, that have successfully been used in other industry sectors before. In other pilot sites fiber optic sensors are deployed to monitor sedimentation, forecasts capabilities of hydrological forecasts are improved and issues with cold ironing supplies are researched. Furthermore, smart buoys will measure the water levels and communicate with a peripheral device to measure the clearance between the bridge span and the water surface as well as water temperature, current speed and direction. In other pilots the buoys will be equipped with tagging devices to find abandoned ones downstream.

These technologies and systems are about to be tested in the pilots, so within these roadmaps it is not possible to clear in advance any suitability or efficiency regarding which available technologies are best suited to realize change while minimizing risks. The project aims at spreading and connect the pilot’s activities out of the consortium through a Living Lab approach.

The roadmaps cannot be fully generic, and not necessarily easily applied in all other inland waterway regions, as they are dedicated towards the pilots. However, some aspects of processes and measures planned may serve as a blueprint/ for other regions.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 Alignment of D1.3 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D1.3 Roadmaps as Blueprints for Wider Applicability and Use	<i>This deliverable will define the main aspects of the strategic vision, as requirements, solutions, current and future operations and economic risks of stakeholders.</i>	<i>all</i>	<i>This deliverable includes the findings from the task 1.4 and 1.5, while also referring to sources like D 1.1, D1.2, D 4.1 and D5.1 as well as the pilot scenarios description produced in WP6. Results of task 1.2 are included as well.</i>
TASKS			

<p>Task 1.5 Roadmaps as Blueprints for Wider Applicability and Use</p>	<p><i>The resulting roadmaps will outline and prioritize the processes that need to be changed to achieve the vision of much extended deployment possibilities for inland navigation. The resulting roadmap will not be fully generic, and not necessarily easily applied in all other inland waterway regions, as it is dedicated towards the pilots. However, it may serve as a blueprint/ for other regions.</i></p>	<p>3-5</p>	<p><i>The postulated assessment of the technologies and process in terms of their effectiveness cannot be done at this stage of the project.</i></p>
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1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The deliverable summarizes and lists the plans in the pilot sites and displays them in a common format. (Chapters 3-5). Additionally, this deliverable reports the efforts undertaken in task 1.2 regarding the KPI definition (Chapter 6).

2. Set-up of the roadmaps

This is the proposed content of the roadmaps for the CRISTAL pilots. The roadmaps are intended to create transparency about the purpose and process of the development work within the pilots. These aspects would be necessary if the roadmap is to serve a wider applicability and use. Therefore, the roadmaps for each pilot site are presented in a Gantt chart format. The following dimensions should be covered:

1. Scope including short-term and long-term strategies:

This dimension refers to how the overall goals and objectives of the pilot, as well as the specific products, results and/ or deliverables shall be achieved.

2. Timeline:

This dimension includes the pilot's start and end dates, as well as any key milestones resp. deadlines along the implementation path.

3. Budget:

If available, this dimension outlines the pilot's financial resources, including the total cost and how the funds (own money and EU contribution) will be allocated throughout the pilot.

4. Resources:

This dimension includes the people, materials, and equipment needed to complete the pilot successfully regarding the proposed technologies and activities such as FOS, Buoys, AE, Radar inspection, cold ironing, living lab and governance related activities.

5. Risks:

This dimension identifies potential risks that may arise during the pilot and outlines strategies for mitigating or managing them.

It was however not possible to gather all the requested information from each pilot site. Especially the issues budget and resources seem to be still in a process of being not fully defined yet. Since the pilots in the three countries are very different from each other regarding the issues covered, each pilot site is treated separately. Proposed measures and technology might suit other inland waterway infrastructure but that depends on the regional circumstances. The pilots aim at contributing to achieve the overall Cristal goals, which are:

- increase the share of IWT by min. 20%,
- Improve reliability by 80%,
- Assure IWT capacity at 50% even during extreme weather events.

3. Roadmap based on the French pilot site

3.1. Introduction

The purpose of this section is to provide an analysis of the current situation. However, with reference to the work already carried out in Deliverable 1.2, please refer to that assessment of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats as a part of D 1.2.¹

3.2. Goals and Objectives

This section outlines the specific goals and objectives of the pilot and explains how they align with the overall strategic objectives of the project and the organization regarding its role in the project.

VNF as the pilot site owner and the infrastructure authority have the following main goals within its pilot:

- Improve the overall usability and quality of the IWT sector through CEDRE, an Electronic freight documentation tool , IOT to monitor vessel positions and anchorage and improved safety by locating buoys that have become detached and have drifted away
- Improve maintenance efficiency and effectiveness by radar inspection of concrete walls in locks and canals and by acoustic emission monitoring of lock doors

The objectives therefore can be summarized as follows:

- Improve the usability of the IWT system and make the processes more efficient by introducing the CEDRE platform for digital loading documentation
- Barges can be geolocated, and the availability of parking and handling areas can be known through IOT.
- Maintenance efficiency and effectiveness can be improved by remotely monitoring and managing buoys, inspecting locks with radar, and monitoring dams using acoustic emission techniques, in particular
 - Obtain more recent and more accurate data about the status of the concrete walls through radar inspection through a 3 to 5 year routine scan.
 - Obtain insights on possible technological or structural problems arising in the movements of the lock door through analysis via the acoustic emission system.

3.3. Strategies and Tactics

This section outlines the specific strategies and tactics that will be used to achieve the objectives of the roadmap. It includes details such as timeline, budgets, and resource requirements.

¹ SWOT analysis for each pilot site documented in Deliverable 1.2, Stakeholder Assessment and Key Innovative Technology Assessment

Strategy 1: Introduce the CEDRE platform

The following objectives have been formulated for the CEDRE platform

- The platform should be connected to the transport management system of large companies and allow individual shipowners to declare cargo shipments.
- It should issue digitised transport documents, secured and editable by authorised parties.
- It could give authorised customers (shippers or forwarders) access to information on empty barges.

Steps:

- Obtain the agreement of the river transport companies for the creation of gateways between their systems and the VNF information system: first half of 2023
- Describe the data content and the flow of transport documents between freight operators. 2023
- A demonstrator web service will be created with the agreement of at least one of the companies 2023
- Transform the VNF system to open it up to principals or charterers. 2023
- Definition of specifications for the creation of an online service for the creation and updating of transport documents (bills of lading or waybills) 2023
- Creation of an online service for creating and updating transport documents (bills of lading or waybills)2024
- The advisability and feasibility of setting up a system for the sharing of data on cargoes available to authorised persons (in particular charterers) could be studied. 2025.

Strategy 2: Geolocate barges on the network

Description:

- Barges which are not subject to the AIS obligation must be geolocated
- The service could be free for the manager and users who have a geolocation system, interfaceable with the information systems of managers and other stakeholders.
- Recommendations for geolocation standards could be proposed.
- Users should know the availability of parking and handling areas: camera on the platform and AI detection to train should be tested
- A demonstrator site should be created on the Louis Blériot wharf (Haropa manager) where unused barges present nuisances for local residents (issues of monitoring wharf occupancy, barge storage, adaptation of the police regulations of navigation). An artificial intelligence, trained in the “laboratory”, should be tested on the demonstrator site.

Steps:

- A demonstration site should be built on the Seine: 2023
- A report could be produced on the use of artificial intelligence to detect and transmit information on the occupation of quays by a boat or barge: 2024

Strategy 3: Geolocate buoys in case of drifting

Description:

- The buoys that mark the waterway are affected by strong currents and, above all, by floods (during and after them).
- After a flood, the VNF must be able to identify as quickly as possible which buoys have left their moorings and are drifting down the river, so that they can be repositioned as quickly as possible to ensure safe navigation. If they take longer, they must be identified, and the information passed on to the waterway users.
- Remote monitoring and management of buoys and automation of information dissemination should be implemented.
- The data includes the position of the buoy and the status of the buoy light.

Steps:

- An experiment will be carried out on the transboundary stretch of the Apach : narrow channel with buoys regularly damaged (floods, congestion, boats).
- The dissemination of information to users by AvisBat will be standardised.
- The prioritisation of the buoy equipment (160 buoys on 150 km of the Moselle) will be studied for possible deployment.
- A report will be drawn up to propose a format for intelligent buoys, which could address the following issues
 - Standardisation of user information
 - Choice of satellite network for positioning
 - An experiment should be carried out on the transboundary reach of the Apach: 2023

A report could be drawn up to propose a format for such smart buoys: 2024

Strategy 4: Check the integrity of the concrete walls within the lock

Description:

- Radar inspection systems use non-invasive testing techniques to evaluate the integrity of concrete walls, and other structures. The basic principle behind radar inspection is that when a radar signal is directed at a surface, it will reflect back differently depending on the composition and thickness of the material being inspected.

- In the case of concrete walls, radar inspection systems typically use high-frequency electromagnetic waves to penetrate the surface of the concrete and evaluate its internal structure. The system consists of a radar antenna, which is mounted on a scanning device that moves along the surface of the wall being inspected. The radar antenna emits high-frequency signals that penetrate the concrete and reflect back to the antenna, where they are processed and analysed by the system's software.
- The radar inspection system can detect variations in the density and composition of the concrete, as well as the location and depth of any embedded objects or defects, such as cracks or voids. The system can produce detailed images of the internal structure of the concrete, allowing inspectors to identify any potential problems and assess the overall condition of the structure.
- Radar inspection systems are particularly useful for evaluating concrete walls and other structures that are difficult or impossible to inspect visually. They can help identify areas of weakness or damage in concrete walls, allowing for timely repairs and maintenance to ensure the long-term structural integrity of the building or structure.
- Overall, radar inspection systems are a valuable tool for the non-destructive evaluation of concrete walls and other structures, providing inspectors with detailed information on the internal condition of the material without the need for invasive testing or destructive sampling.

Steps: To achieve the goal of an improved maintenance efficiency and effectiveness by radar inspection of concrete walls in locks and canals includes the following set-up:

- The lock will be emptied
- The radar inspection device will be put into the dry lock. The methodology does not work sub surface the water.
- The device scans the concrete walls in a non-inversive manner. Usually drill holes are necessary to assess the status of the concrete walls, which damages the walls in various places and only produces an exact result on the spots of the drills.
- The data of the radar scan is assessed.
- The status of the walls is calculated and assessed.

This procedure can be repeated in a at 3 to 5 annual routine, to monitor the decay of the concrete walls if any.

Strategy 5: Monitor the operations of the lock doors with the Acoustic Emission system (AE)

Description:

- Locks are a critical part of the inland waterway infrastructure. Some have only one lock chamber, larger ones have two lock chambers, three is an absolute exception. So, there is not much of a spare capacity if a lock fails. A non-function of the lock structure would block a link entirely. Even if one chamber remains operational, it would mean a capacity constraint, since lockings take a fixed time per vessel and cannot be made faster. That is why a preventive maintenance by checking the structure and in the case of AE monitoring the function of the doors and possibly

the pumps improves reliability of the whole inland waterway link. Since the locks also function for water management, they serve this additional role in the case of extreme weather events.

- Acoustic emission systems are used to monitor and to evaluate the integrity of machinery and structures by detecting high-frequency stress waves produced by the materials under load. The basic principle behind acoustic emission testing is that when a material is subjected to a load or stress, it will produce acoustic waves or emissions, which can be detected and analysed for potential defects or anomalies.
- The acoustic emission system typically consists of one or more sensors, which are placed on the surface of the machinery being monitored. These sensors are designed to detect the high-frequency stress waves generated by the machinery during operation. The sensors are connected to a computerized data acquisition system, which records and analyses the signals received from the sensors.
- During operation, the acoustic emission system continuously monitors the machinery for any indications of stress wave emissions. If a defect or anomaly is detected, the system can alert the operator to take corrective action. Acoustic emission systems are particularly useful for detecting early warning signs of damage or wear in machinery, which can help prevent catastrophic failures and extend the life of the equipment.

Steps:

- Installation of AE unit at lock(s) like at Seine (Méricourt, Poses-Amfreville) or Moselle
- In every case collection and analysis data in the stand-alone system
- A double AE system will be deployed performing micro-crack calibration, water leakage simulation (if applicable) and general gate good operation measurements.
- Data will then be processed and mined for extracting corresponding features which will be the one transmitted to the digital twin through a data broker.
- ML models will then provide alarm or defect notice and prediction on failure. These models as part of the digital twin will proceed with the following AE specific services:
 - Defect prediction with proper display-ability on the functional state of lock gates
 - Alert System - Lock Gate: Alert on lock door failure

Strategy 6: Spread and connect the pilot's activities out of the consortium through a Living Lab approach

After the identification of the first 5 strategies, that can be defined as the “Core elements” of the French pilot site and in accordance with the principles and targets of the Cristal project, the French Living Lab will be activated.

Step1: Each Strategy/core element leader will identify what is required of the Living Lab:

- Gathering information
- Spread Knowledge
- Awareness raising campaign
- Advocacy with local actors and policy makers

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Step2: Stakeholders' individuation per each Living Lab event

Step3: WP4 training on Living Lab features and implementation

Step4: Events (webinars, workshops, calls, in person events...) organization

Step5: Reporting

Step6: Living Lab Achievements (i.e., manifesto of intents, long term agreements, letter of intent, etc..)

Figure 1: French pilot roadmap

3.4. Involvement of stakeholders

The involvement of stakeholders is an important factor in the CRISTAL project. However, a sensible integration of stakeholders requires first a fixed set-up of the pilot's strategies, in order to add the stakeholders to the process in a way, that both parties benefit from. These are the plans re. the stakeholder integration.

Table 2: Stakeholders in the French pilot

Infrastructure managers	Rail	SNCF réseau
	Road	SANEF/SAPN ; région Grand Est
	IWT	VNF
Transport companies	Shipping line	
	Trucks	Mauffrey/MGE/Transports Vigneron/Transports Foulon
	Rail freight operators	SNCF + others
	Barge operators	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transtest, Specherei...
Inland terminal	Terminal operator	Seine : Haropa, Moselle : The company managing the whole is the syndicat mixte pour la gestion des ports
Deepsea ports	Terminal operator	
	Port authority	Seine : Haropa
	etc.	
Logistics service providers	1, 2, 3 or 4 PL (producers delivers	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transtest, Specherei
	5PL (= 4PL + view on network rather than	
Shipper / cargo owner	Sender	depends on the needs (in waiting of the questionnaire)
	receiver	depends on the needs (in waiting of the questionnaire)
Regulators of IWT	Federal government	Ministères chargés de l'économie, du budget, des transports, de l'agriculture, du tourisme, de l'énergie, de
	Local government	Communauté Urbaine Le Havre ; Seine métropole ; métropole du Grand Nancy ; CCNR ; CIM (Commission
People	Citizens living near the waterway	
	Environmental group(s)	France nature environnement, or more depending on the needs

	Local interest groups	
Sector organisations	Farmers	
	Power plants	Syndicat des énergies renouvelables
	Tourism sector	
	Transport sector	Entreprises fluviales de France
		Union des Chargeurs de Lorraine
		Organisation des PME du transport routier
		Association des utilisateurs de transport de fret
		Union des transporteurs publics et ferroviaires
		Fédération nationale des transports routiers
		Union des Entreprises de Transport et de Logistique de France

3.5. Tangible barriers and opportunities

Quality of data obtained

Both the CEDRE development and the IOT for geolocation of barges need to be fully integrated into the project plan.

Both methods for the infrastructure surveillance, the radar inspection system and the acoustic emission system, are already tried and tested methods, but in different areas of application than in inland navigation. Both applications are research projects that have yet to prove their suitability for the purpose chosen here. This means that it may well be that in one or the other case, or in both, the data obtained is not suitable for drawing well-founded conclusions about the condition of the concrete walls in the lock or the lock gates. This represents a risk.

Established routines

For the barges geolocation it has to be evaluated, if not existing methods of AIS positioning system and data analysis methods would lead to a leaner solution.

Infrastructure examinations will not have to be carried out continuously, but at an interval of several years, which is still to be determined. What this could mean is a significant increase in the security of the availability of the infrastructure elements examined in this way.

Economics

The infrastructure tests will also have to prove whether they are economically viable. Previous methods of examining concrete walls in maritime areas are based on test drilling. Whether the radar inspection system is more economical to use still must be proven. Same goes for the Acoustic Emission system.

Legal framework

It has to be proven if these new methods for infrastructure maintenance are accepted in the legal framework or are at least treated in the same way as the established methods with drilling and drivers' inspections as suitable measures for infrastructure maintenance.

Overall opportunities

However, these methods, if they prove their worth, can very well contribute to better monitoring the infrastructure of inland waterways and thus prevent sudden failures caused by defective elements.

4. Roadmap based on the Italian pilot site

4.1. Introduction

This section will analyse the current situation with reference to the work carried out in Deliverable 1.2, which already includes an evaluation of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT analysis) for each pilot site. The SWOT analysis is documented in Deliverable 1.2, which covers Stakeholders Evaluation and Key Innovative Technology Assessment.

4.2. Specific goals of the Italian pilot

This section outlines the specific goals and objectives of the roadmap and explains how they align with the overall strategic objectives of the project and the organization regarding its role in the project.

The Italian partners, IV, and AiPo AIPO (Inland waterway infrastructure operator), ENEA and CERTH (technology providers), SOGESCA (sustainable development engineering company) and Unioncamere/Uniontrasporti, (representing the Chamber of Commerce), have the following goals within their respective pilot activities (not all partners will participate to each activity):

- Improve the reliability of the information about the navigability of the river and its forecast, through:
 - measurement of the riverbed sediment thickness, through FOS fiber optic sensors (operational testing).
 - Improvement of the hydraulic model regarding shallow waters.
- Provide better information to users thanks to the smart bulletin.
- Analyse the feasibility of cold ironing facilities for decarbonisation and emission reduction.
- Improve maintenance efficiency and effectiveness of lock door monitoring using AE acoustic emission sensor and Machine learning algorithm for the automatic detection of cracks and deterioration mechanisms.
- Improve sensibility towards the topics of resilience and business continuity providing an overview of guidelines, European directives and international standards regarding the sustainability and the resilience to climate change of the Italian pilot's organizations (public and private).
- Involve stakeholders to gather information, spread knowledge, raise awareness from the population level to the policy makers level through a Living Lab activation.

The objectives therefore can be summarized as follows:

- Test, if monitoring of real time sedimentation in the Po River through FOS as input to the navigation status would be possible through laboratory tests of the FOS
- Stretch the forecasted period of the navigability model at +5 and +10 days, through improved data input and model calculations
- Obtain more recent and more accurate data about the status of the lock doors through Acoustic Emission system

- Carry out a feasibility study regarding cold ironing opportunities for barges.
- Perform a GAP Analysis on 10 private companies and 5 public bodies with respect to the guidelines described in D3.2 to identify their distance from a reliable, sustainable and climate change resilience condition and propose some improvements.
- Carry on different events (webinar, workshops, interview, in person events, etc..) to enable the different objectives above mentioned and some milestones with a specific stakeholders' engagement based on the necessities declared by each activity.

4.3.Strategies and Tactics

This section outlines the specific strategies and tactics that will be used to achieve the objectives and objectives of the roadmap. It includes details such as timeline, budgets, and other requirements.

The strategies and tactics aim to achieve the above-mentioned objectives.

Strategy 1: Improve navigability reliability in free-flowing waterways through continuous monitoring

Description:

- Navigability level in a free-flowing waterway is variable, due to the dynamic sedimentation of sand, gravel and debris in the waterway bed; this sedimentation process dynamically changes the availability of the infrastructure by minimising the draught and / or narrowing the fairway. The only accurate way, available at the time being, to measure the height and volume of the sand dunes created by this dynamic sedimentation process is through sound boots that can measure the bearings of the water. This operation happens in the Po River once daily for selected critical sections and it is quite time and resource intensive and does not allow to have a continuous monitoring of the situations that might change in different times within the same day.
- For the Italian inland waterway segments, based on the daily sound boot measurements, a forecast navigability bulletin is issued daily. AiPo would like to improve the quality of the AIPO navigability bulletin furtherly and to extend the forecasted period thanks to the implementation of a Machine Learning (ML) algorithm (as reported in Strategy 2 below), for forecasting navigability level that will be developed in close collaboration between AIPO, ENEA and FHG as part of Task 7.5.
- The FOS sensors, by measuring the weight of the sediments, can monitor in a constant and continuous way the changes in height and possibly in the volume of these dunes that might impede/challenge the navigability.
- The tests to validate FOS technology for the purpose will be performed in a laboratory and operation environment, no installation on the real environment of FOS will be envisioned within CRISTAL project as clearly stated in CRISTAL grant.
- In the future FOS data and other additional data can be integrated in the ML navigability model.

Steps:

- Desk study, TRL 1-3 of the FOS sensors to qualitatively analyse the functionality of the FOS sensors to support the monitoring of the movement of the sediments in the Po riverbed. It includes the proposed metrics, Performance Indicators (PI), which are identified with the strain measured by the FOS;
 - An analytical model that allows to estimate the height and shape of the sediments from the PI measured by the FOS.
 - A qualitative assessment guided and carried out through an innovation questionnaire or an ad hoc workshop.
 - The expected outcome of this first step is to obtain a clear description of the intended functionality of the FOS sensors (e.g. design criteria), the identification of possible failure modes, a preliminary theoretical assessment of social acceptance and an initial screening of the potential impact of the innovation on different sectors relevant to IWW.
- Laboratory testing, TRL 4-5
 - In this phase, the FOS is analysed based on the design criteria identified in the desk study. Laboratory testing of the technical PI is carried out and, for those impacts that require further testing, a simple semi-quantitative or more detailed qualitative impact assessment is carried out. A preliminary social acceptance check is carried out, which may be based on interactions with representative stakeholder groups.
- Operational testing, TRL 6-8
 - In this phase, the innovation is analysed against the constraints associated with the (intended) operational and market environment. This phase consists of analysing the PI under operational constraints and demonstrating the performance of the innovation when placed in a simulated operational environment and/or during real events. A more detailed impact assessment may be carried out using existing site conditions. Social acceptance testing may be conducted with stakeholders or end-users from the environment in which the innovation is to be implemented. These tests are an important step in demonstrating the technical effectiveness and social acceptability of the innovation.

Strategy 2: Improve the hydraulic Navigability forecast model and new smart daily report (bulletin)

AIPO will contribute to CRISTAL activities by developing a forecasting navigability model. This task will realize a hydraulic navigability model implemented using DEWS (Drought Early Warning System) data of discharge, observed, and forecasted at +5 and +10 days. The detailed definition of the technologies to be developed and installed in this purpose is part of the expected outcomes of the study to be carried out. Analysing the data related to the discharges it will be possible to perform an evaluation of water depth and navigability.

Considering historical data set of draught and discharge, coupled with depth and navigation forecasting time series, the daily report will forecast the navigability in the different sections of the Po River (based on the correlation between discharge and draught).

The activity to be carried out by AIPo will address the challenge of providing effective decision support for the main stakeholders to reduce the uncertainty due to the free-flowing settlement of the Po River and climate change. AIPo will focus on the development of a forecast bulletin to provide information on the navigability conditions of the Po River: this information will boost river transport accountability, allowing decision making about initiating a goods delivery through river transport.

Steps:

- Step 1 (Desk study, TRL 1-3)
With reference to Figure 2 two sub-steps will be performed
 - Asking the right question – technical meetings and possibly technology workshop will be organised, the latter in collaboration with WP4
 - Preparing Data - The data currently available includes:
 - Cartographic data of the riverbed and navigable sections.
 - Water and sediment depth and discharge datasets, measured on the main known critical points of the navigation area, from about 1988 until today.
 - Historical flow and level data, at the hydrometers installed.
 - Flow prediction, provided by numerical water management models.

- Step 2 (Laboratory testing, TRL 4-5)
With reference to Figure 2 two sub-steps will be performed.
 - 2.2 Selecting the algorithm - navigability model
 - 2.3 Training the model - navigability model

- Step 3 (Operational testing, TRL 6-8)
With reference to Figure 2 the following step will be performed.
 - 3.1 Testing the model - navigability model

Figure 2: Possible workflow for developing the CRISTAL ML navigability algorithm

The three steps above will be followed by further steps related to how to provide the information developed to the users (smart bulletin):

- Step 4 – Navigability bulletin of river stretches
- Step 5 – Study of the possibility of integrating the navigability bulletin into the RIS Italy
- Step 6 – Integration of navigability bulletin data into Cristal Synchromodal platform

Given the nature of AiPo's pilot project, the whole set of expected studies represents most of the budget committed by AiPo to the CRISTAL project. In more detail, the budget table related to these activities includes the following rough subdivision, which will be further refined according to the finalised assignments.

Table 3: Estimated Budget for AiPo's tasks in WP7

Activities/Task	External Expertise	Staff (Indicative)	Total	Status
7.2 / Contract to external experts to define the statistical/hydraulic model of shallow waters Completion of the expected deliverable.	10.000 €	35.000 €	45.000 €	Currently ongoing
7.2 / Contract to external expertise to realize a dedicated feasibility study to define a +5/+10-day forecast bulletin relating to the navigability conditions of the river Po	15.000 €	40.000 €	55.000 €	Both to be launched after because of the assignment 1
7.2 // Contract to external expertise to realize a +10-day forecast bulletin (in according with the feasibility study) relating to the navigability conditions of the river Po	25.000 €	40.000 €	65.000 €	

All these figures are obviously estimations, while detailed data will be provided once the assignments will be completed.

Strategy 3: Monitor the operations of the lock doors with the Acoustic Emission system (AE)

The Acoustic emission system is the same already described for the French pilot site (sub-chapter 3.3 – Strategy 5). CERTH will install AE systems in some locks owned by AIPO and IV to test the automatic detection of damages and deterioration of the lock doors.

AIPO and IV will provide the access to their respective infrastructures (locks) and the local assistance during the measurements. In this process WP2 (Leader: ENEA) is also involved for the aspects related both to the "Software architecture of CRISTAL acquisition system" (task 2.3) while WP5 is involved for the "Digital Twin" (task 7.5).

Steps

- Inspection of the lock of "Conca di Baricetta ", managed by Infrastrutture Venete (to plan the following AE measurement campaign) and then of the lock "Isola Serafini" managed by AIPO.
- Installation of the AE system and measurements at the lock "Conca di Baricetta" and then at the locks "Isola Serafini".
 - The AE system, as a monitoring system, generates raw data per hit occurrence with an adjustable threshold, which is reduced to features such as energy, duration, counts, partial frequency power, average frequency, instantaneous frequency and phase, trigger frequency and various other technical features/indicators that show the functional state of the lock doors/gates. This data is transferred to the Digital Twin (DT).
- Feasibility check if it is possible to derive from the data an alarm system for the lock doors (performed by WP5).
 - The results of the analysis of the generated AE system data could be used to implement an alarm system for lock doors. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT alert system for a specific lock door with a custom threshold for a parameter (e.g., possible gate failure probability). The system will then monitor this parameter and, as soon as the threshold is exceeded, a notification will be sent to the subscriber. This can be used, for example, by the infrastructure manager to check the status of the lock and to schedule further inspections and/or maintenance. The subscribers and thresholds are stored. The results are made available to the subscribers (e.g., CMS, AIPO Dashboard) and the DT Smart Monitor.
- Relative to the AE use cases as described in deliverable 5.1. They include the following functions:
 - Display of outputs
 - Alert System – Lock Gate
 - Gate Lock failure prediction
 - Lock chamber dimensions (user input, not an output by the AE)

Strategy 4: Proving feasibility of cold ironing for decarbonisation and emission reduction

Decarbonisation is an overall EU policy goal, lately formulated in the Fit for 55 strategy². If vessels are electrified and run with electric engines powered by on-board batteries, they need on shore power supply here referred to as cold ironing. Cold ironing however could also mean that the boats can at least switch of their diesel engines while staying in a port or waiting in front of a lock. In that sense the cold ironing serves primarily the reduction of emissions like NO_x, SO_x, particles and CO₂.

The overall commitment of Infrastrutture Venete Srl within the Cristal pilot is represented by the development of a feasibility study on the development of cold ironing facilities along the Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante e Po – Brondolo IWW. More in particular such studies are going to be organized as follows:

- Step 1: Currently launched, a dedicated assignment will be organized to identify an external expert in charge of:
 - Developing the tendering procedures for the technical activities of study.
 - Following and coordinating such studies
 - Reporting the results of the studies according to the templates/requests of the CRISTAL project
 - Confronting and giving feedbacks to other WPs with reference to the results of the studies and of the activities carried out.
- Step 2: To be launched and activated in June 2023 an assignment for external expert/subcontractor in charge of developing the feasibility study aimed at understanding:
 - How to plan the installation of cold ironing points along IV's waterway, taking into consideration not only its performance characteristics and the infrastructure as a whole, but also
 - The potential derived from the possible use of renewable energies that can adequately power the cold ironing infrastructures to be created, in full synergy with the territories crossed by the infrastructure.
 - Moreover, the assignment should also provide for the definition of a sort of logical framework to be used for the choice of whether or not to make this type of investment in a given point according to the specifics of that point analysed through the tool/logic proposed by the feasibility study.
 - This last activity will represent a strong added value for the project itself which will be able to deliver a tool to efficiently spread the specific knowledge gained in other territories/contexts.
- Step 3 – To be launched and activated in February 2024 an assignment for external expert/subcontractor in charge of developing the design of a "typical plant" model of cold ironing facility.

² EU Commission; Communication: 'Fit for 55' - delivering the EU's 2030 climate target on the way to climate neutrality, Brussels 2021

- This activity will be necessarily launched once part of the analysis activity referred to in the above point has been clarified / deepened. It will be an activity that will be carried out as a consequence of the point above, and the possible complementarity with respect to other specific initiatives launched by Infrastrutture Venete Srl will also be verified into detail.

Table 4: Estimated budget for the cold ironing activities

Activities/Task	External Expertise	Staff (Indicative)	Total	Status
7.2 / Contract to external expertise to sum-up the results of the studies, analysis, and template design to define a joint roadmap for the development of the future cold-ironing facilities along the IWW. Completion of the expected deliverable.	34.000 €	12.000 €	36.000 €	Just assigned. Currently ongoing
7.2 / Contract to external expertise to realize a dedicated feasibility study (including financial perspectives) for the equipment of IWW with cold ironing facilities and related contribution of renewable energies within the territories involved by IV.	72.000 €	17.000 €	89.000 €	To be launched asap as a consequence of the assignment 1 (estimate 06/2023)
7.2 / Contract to external expertise to realize a dedicated design of cold ironing facility to equip berths and ports in the IWW with related examples and template.	50.000 €	25.000 €	75.000 €	To be launched as a consequence of assignment 2 (02/2024)

All these figures are forecasts, while detailed data will be provided once the assignments will be completed.

Strategy 5: Provide with knowledge and methods the organizations belonging to the IWT&L Italian pilot system to better sustain, adapt and react to the man-made and climate change disruptions

Inland navigation is exposed to the consequences of the suspected climate change and must respond to increasing demands to adapt to regulatory developments.

Step1: SOGESCA will approach provide to some the Italian pilot stakeholders to present an overview of the guidelines (D3.2) related to:

- International and European initiatives and drivers
- Common aspects of management systems
- Tools to support public bodies (e.g., SECAP – Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan)
- Sustainability report ESG (environmental, social and governance)
- Carbon footprint and mitigation
- Adaptation to climate change
- Business continuity, emergency management and synchronicity

Step2: SOGESCA will perform a Gap Analysis to 10 volunteered private companies and 5 public bodies (mainly ports and municipalities) to highlight their strengths, their weaknesses, the possibilities of improvement, with respect to international standards on central issues such as environmental sustainability and adaptation to climate change.

The evaluation will be tailored according to the type of organization: municipality, private company or port authority.

A report will be delivered with the results of the evaluation and some advice of intervention.

Strategy 6: Spread a connect the pilot's activities out of the consortium through a Living Lab approach

After the identification of the first 5 strategies, that can be defined as the “Core elements” of the Italian pilot site and in accordance with the principles and targets of the Cristal project, SOGESCA in cooperation with Unioncamere/Unioni Trasporti will activate and manage the Italian Living Lab.

Step1: Each Strategy/core element leader will identify what is required of the Living Lab:

- Gathering information
- Spread Knowledge
- Awareness raising campaign
- Advocacy with local actors and policy makers

Step2: Stakeholders' individuation per each Living Lab event

Step3: Events (webinars, workshops, calls, in person events) organization

Step 4: Reporting

Step 5: Living Lab Achievements (e.i. manifesto of intents, long term agreements, letter of intent, etc..)

Figure 3: Italian pilot site roadmap

4.4. Stakeholders' integration

The potential stakeholders for the Italian pilot sites have been identified (see in table 5 the indicative list).

In the activities of the pilot, the involvement of the stakeholders is an important factor, but a sensible integration of stakeholders requires first a fixed set-up of the pilot's strategies, to add the stakeholders to the process in a way, that both parties benefit from.

However, it should be remembered that the involvement of a stakeholder in the project will be a decision of the stakeholder himself or herself. The Italian pilot sites owner plan the following inclusion of the stakeholders

Table 5: Stakeholders in the Italian pilot (indicative list)

Infrastructure Manager	Rail	RFI, Infrastrutture Venete
	Road	Core Network highways close to the IWW: Autostrada del Brennero Spa (A22 Brennero-Modena), Autostrade per l'Italia Spa (A1 Milano-Bologna, A13 Bologna-Padova) Comprehensive Network highways close to the IWW: Autovia padana Spa (A21 Brescia-Piacenza) Anas; Provinces/municipalities for local roads; Veneto strade spa.
	IWT	AlPo (realising and maintaining the infrastructures to ensure the free-flow navigation along the Po River from Piacenza to Adriatic Sea) Infrastrutture Venete (realising and maintaining the infrastructures for the navigationn along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante, Po di Brondolo and Litornarea Veneta waterway)
Transport companies	Associations	
	Shipping line	Not regular tourist line services: Altobordo Srl (Motonave Stradivari), River Cruises SRL (Cremona Crociere)
	Trucks	Some of the logistics services providers own their own trucks; local trucks owners. (See logistics service providers)
	Rail freight operators	Mercitalia (RFI Group), HUPAC, Sograp (Porto di Cremona), FS logistica (Porto di Mantova)
	Barge operators	Fagioli Spa, Tecno Service Chioggia, Fluviomar Srl, Omniariver, Transmar Venezia, Caronte Shipping, Ship Service Venezia s.r.l.

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Rail-road terminal	Terminal operators	Interporto Quadrante Europa (Verona), Interporto di Bologna spa, Interporto Padova Spa Several terminals in Milano Area.
IWW Ports		Port of Cremona, Port of Mantova Valdaro, Port of Rovigo
	Terminal operators	Portuali Valdaro S.r.l. (Mantova Valdaro Port - also barge operator)
	Port authority	Province of Cremona (Cremona Port), Provincia di Mantova (Mantova Valdaro Port), Ispettorato di Porto (Rovigo Port)
Deepsea ports		Port of Venice and Ravenna port
	Terminal operators	Several operators in Venice Port and Ravenna port
	Port authority	ADSP Mare Adriatico Settentrionale (Venezia Port) ADSP Mare adriatico Centro Settentrionale (Ravenna Port) ASDP Mare Adriatico Orientale (Trieste Port)
Logistics service providers	1 PL (producer delivers cargo to client, own trucks/vessels)	Paganella Spa, Generation Transport spa, Katoen Natie, Fercam, ASTL Logistica Srl, TCF Rosignoli Logistics, Borsari & C Srl, Fagioli Spa (oversize loads), River Service Srl, Maersk, Servizi, Portuali Valdaro S.r.l. (Mantova Port)
	2 PL (producer delivers cargo via transport company)	
	3PL (outsourcing of logistics to a third party)	
	4PL (outsource all of the organisation and oversight of their supply chain and logistics to one external provider which has no own assets)	
Shipper / cargo owner	Sender/receiver	Consorzio Agrario, Arvedi Spa, Belleli Energy, Marcegaglia, Gruppo Saviola, MOL
Regulators of IWT	EU	Yes – Please note that Po River is still not considered a transnational IWW system
	Country government	Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti: Inland navigation management
	Local government (Regional)	Lombardy Region, Emilia-Romagna Region, Veneto Region, Piedmont Region: responsible for the development of the inland waterway in their respective territory (Interregional agreement on inland navigation to coordinate the actions)
	Basin Authorities	Autorità di Bacino Distrettuale del Fiume Po: flood protection and water resources management (refers to the Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica)

People	Citizens living near the waterway	
	Environmental group(s)	WWF, Legambiente, Associazione Persona Ambiente
	Local interest groups	Propeller Club Mantova, UNII
	Civil Protections Organisation	National and Regional Civil Protection Departments and Civil Protection Offices within Municipalities
Sector organisations representing private companies		Camere di commercio, Unioncamere and Unitransporti
	Farmers	Associations: Confagricoltura, Coldiretti, CIA, Libera associazione agricoltori cremonesi
	Power plants	ENEL
	Tourism sector	<i>Not regular tourist line services:</i> Altobordo Srl (Motonave Stradivari), River Cruises SRL (Cremona Crociere), Motonavi Andes Negrini (mantova) Several other companies operating on Laguna Veneta and other section of the Padano-Veneto IWW (not in the area selected for the pilot)
	Shipyards	C.N.P, Cantiere Navale Visentini, Cantiere Navale Vittoria, CGX Costruzioni Generali XODO Srl
	Others	Rowing Clubs, several other associations for sporting purpose.
Universities	University 1	E.g. UniVersità Ca' Foscari, Università degli studi di Padova, Università di Parma, Università di Mantova, Politecnico di Milano. Several related projects funded by PNRR
	University 2	
Knowledge institutes	Knowledge institute 1	Corila (consortium)

4.5. Tangible barriers and opportunities

Technical issues

- FOS for sediments have not yet been tested in a real river environment, so their impact remains speculative at this point of time in research.
- Some technologies may prove to be unsuitable for the IWT environment or technical issues arise for their development /implementation. Any effort will be made to assure that the technologies will be conceived since the very beginning to be compatible and adaptable with the very peculiar IWT conditions.

Methodology

- Considering the nature of the activities regarding the hydraulic modelling the risks could arise from verifying the reliability of the forecasting model by comparing the forecast data with daily surveyed data in order to make the forecast model reliable.
- Moreover, an additional potential risk could arise from unforeseen requests coming from other WPs that would potentially slow down the expected studies, even if without affecting the overall objective/result.

Economics

- The risk of a delay in availability of financial means and/ or materials for realizing the technologies is considered low, given the duration of three years of the project. Even a delay of one year in implementation still allows a full year testing cycle.
- It could be, that the stakeholders do not accept the proposed technologies or show a general lack of interest on the proposed technologies. WP2 will work closely with WP1, WP4 and WP6 to mitigate if not eliminate this risk.

Legal framework

- Legislative/environmental constraints may limit the use of technologies. Any effort will be made to assure that the technologies will be environmentally friendly, sustainable and compliant with legislative requirements and standards. Technologies which will operate constantly in the water like the FOS, must meet the environmental requirements. For FOS a liaison with organisations/experts who realise technologies for offshore uses is aimed at.

5. Roadmap based on the Polish pilot site

5.1. Introduction

This section shall provide an analysis of the current situation. However, with reference to the work undertaken in Deliverable 1.2, we refer to assessment of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (the SWOT analysis for each pilot site, which is documented in Deliverable 1.2., Stakeholders Evaluation and Key Innovative Technology Assessment.

5.2. Specific goals of the Polish pilot

The Polish test site also test and deploys technologies, here the smart buoys, however, this pilot site puts the logistics and the supply chain issues into focus. The main aim is to show that IWT is both technically and organisationally possible as well as economically worthwhile on the lower Vistula River.

The maiden voyage of a container barge on the Vistula River in 2021, conducted as part of the EMMA Extension (Interreg South Baltic) project, showed that local companies in the river pilot area are interested in IWT as a solution for their supply chains. The project parties involved in the voyage received substantial market feedback with the needs of cargo owners to develop and give efforts towards rebuilding the supply chains with the use of IWT based on the existing infrastructure.

Therefore, the main objective of the Polish pilot is to establish and test new supply chain models with implemented IWT solutions under market conditions. The models will identify and verify the factors that allow the selection of cargoes and supply chains most suitable for IWT implementation under current navigation conditions on selected routes, including

- Terms of delivery
- Cargo volume
- Flow frequency
- Time flexibility

The pilot, consisting of four different activities with different types of cargo, selected based on the above-mentioned market indications, will verify the usability of inland navigation within the current infrastructure availability and outline the most necessary investments in the pilot areas. The journey parameters will be compared with the other modes currently used (road or rail) in terms of capacity, transit time and market availability.

The secondary objective of the pilot is to develop and implement the technology of intelligent buoys to provide real-time navigation parameters on selected waterways and to improve the visibility of supply chains with tracking devices that allow the monitoring of traffic on the waterways.

The innovations introduced in the pilot projects should lead to an increase in the share of inland navigation in selected supply chains of up to 20%. According to the expected impact of the CRISTAL project, pre-project studies show that for some groups of goods, proper transport planning and scheduling can allow a shift from pure road transport to inland navigation. Proper planning is only

possible with a developed and tested decision support system based on real-time data provided by innovative technologies, i.e., intelligent buoys. The creation and successful implementation of supply chain models (during the pilot events) will encourage companies located in the pilot areas to focus on inland navigation and consider it as a stable and safe solution for their cargo, despite the deficits in infrastructure and the years of investment required to bring inland navigation in Poland up to AGN standards.

5.3. Strategies and Tactics

This section outlines the specific strategies and tactics that will be used to achieve the goals and objectives of the roadmap. It includes details such as timeline, budgets, and resource requirements.

The strategies and tactics aim to achieve the above-mentioned objectives.

Strategy 1: Establish and test new supply chain models with implemented IWT solutions under market conditions

Step 1: Tender preparation,

- Defining the framework in which the transport chain should be operated. Pilot envisages four voyages with different types of cargo to comprehensively test the suitability of the supply chain models developed. Pre-project research indicated that the most common goods transported between the seaport in Gdansk and the pilot area (Kujawsko-Pomorskie Voivodeship):
 - Containers
 - Fertilizers – packed in Big Bags
 - Grain – in bulk

Fourth voyage performed on Odra (Oder) river will be performed with the containerized cargo. As a part of Intra European supply chains freight forwarder should use 45'PW containers which are most suitable intermodal units, alternative for semitrailers used on European road transport.

- The freight forwarder's responsibility includes the selection of carriers and handling partners with the appropriate equipment to carry out the pilots. The initial and final stages of transport are carried out by road using trucks. The main leg is arranged with the tug and barges suitable for containerised or unitised cargo and hopper barges for bulk cargo.
- Cargo handling process at seaport terminals will be performed using terminal owned equipment – cranes or reachstackers. Operations arranged on river quay, due to insufficient infrastructure, will require to use additional mobile handling equipment loaders and cranes arranged by chosen freight forwarder.

Step 2: Tender execution: This fixes the pilot set-up and the pilot preparation. It includes meeting and contractual findings with the stakeholders which must become subcontractors.

Step 3: Design & Implementation.

- It includes steps like cargo preparation, subcontracts with carriers, securing loading locations, seaport notification, KPI collection and voyage plan incl. pre haul, reloading at POL, seaport notification, voyage plan, delivery
- The pilot voyages will provide a comprehensive view of the existing supply chain configuration and verify the usability of IWT in modern logistics focused on flexibility and transparency. A set of KPIs has been developed to measure the results and compare the newly built supply chains with the solutions currently in use.

Step 4: Validation of results, incl. KPI collection, final reports

Strategy 2: Intelligent buoys to provide real-time navigation parameters

Step 1: Buoys technology elements development and assembly (done in WP2)

Step 2: Buoys installation and operation

- Intelligent buoys (or sensors) placed along the route will provide information on the sailing conditions on the river. Temperature, wind, water speed, depth, and bridge clearance (if any). The sensors will send the received data to a common cloud and will be shared with the appropriate stakeholders (infrastructure manager -> inland navigation operator -> freight forwarder).
- Such data will allow an inland navigation operator (and freight forwarder) to decide to proceed with the barge voyage or to use an alternative mode of transport (rail or truck) to ensure the proper flow of cargo in supply chains despite the obstacles caused by extreme weather conditions or disruptions on the barge route. In addition, the multiplication of sensors will make it possible to calculate transit time and estimate barge arrivals for better supply chain visibility and terminal operations planning. The measured transit time will also provide the input to compare current solutions in supply chains based on road/rail (as is) vs. supply chain built on IW solution.
- The technology implemented will improve the availability of data on sailing conditions required by barge operators. Currently, the data is available on the infrastructure manager's website (not regularly updated) or by telephone. Timely provision of accurate data will speed up the decision-making process initiated by the carrier in its supply chain control tower.

Strategy 3: Spread and connect the pilot's activities out of the consortium through a Living Lab approach

After the identification of the first 2 strategies, that can be defined as the “Core elements” of the Polish pilot site and in accordance with the principles and targets of the Cristal project, the Polish Living Lab will be activated.

Step 1: Each Strategy/core element leader will identify what is required of the Living Lab:

- Gathering information
- Spread Knowledge
- Awareness raising campaign
- Advocacy with local actors and policy makers

Step 2: Stakeholders' individuation per each Living Lab event

Step 3: WP4 training on Living Lab features and implementation

Step 4: Events (webinars, workshops, calls, in person events...) organization

Step 5: Reporting

Step 6: Living Lab Achievements (i.e., manifesto of intents, long term agreements, letter of intent, etc..)

Figure 4: Polish case roadmap

5.4. Involvement of stakeholders

Table 6: Stakeholders in the Polish pilot

Infrastructure manager	IWT	<p>PGW Wody Polskie</p> <p>IWW infrastructure manager, provides the infrastructure for main leg of transport chains, share the knowledge, and cooperates with technology provider on buoys location and its' features. Wody Polskie also manage and administrates the sluices and other hydrotechnical facilities to provide proper navigability class on pilot site. Furthermore, provides information on navigation conditions on IWW. Infrastructure manager is also responsible for collecting the toll for using infrastructure from IWW operator.</p>
	Trucks	<p>Trucking companies – provides first/last mile – road delivery service by the order received from freight forwarder. Depending on chosen business model (and terminals) may be involved in delivery notification at terminals and may cooperate with them directly based on IT solutions developed by terminals.</p>
	Barge operators	<p>IW operator – executes the main leg transport by the order from freight forwarder. Schedules the voyages and notifies infrastructure manager and port authorities on expected schedule and routing.</p>
	Terminal operators	<p>Port Gdansk Eksploatacja, Duisburg or Antwerp terminal</p>
	Port authority	<p>Gdansk Port Authority (GPA) – territory manager at port area. In subject pilot, GPA controls barges traffic at port area, provides the approval for barge approach to indicated port terminals.</p>
Logistics service providers	1 PL (producer delivers cargo to client, own trucks/vessels)	<p>Freight forwarding company – creates the supply chain and execute the pilots based on chosen subcontractors mentioned in subject chapter and</p>

	2 PL (producer delivers cargo via transport company)	created logistics models. Indicates the Loading/delivery terminals and arrange handling and storage solutions in case of insufficient infrastructure availability. Freight forwarder will be also responsible for arranging first/last mile deliveries between terminals and pickup/delivery locations.
	3PL (outsourcing of logistics to a third party)	
	4PL (outsource all of the organisation and oversight of their supply chain and logistics to one external provider which has no own assets)	

5.5. Tangible barriers and opportunities

Technical issues

- The bundled technologies in the Smart Buoys must deliver a real advantage within the inland waterway transport chain. Their raw data must be compiled and visualised both the infrastructure authority and for the potential users.
- The alleged vulnerability against currents may challenge their use in the Vistula river.

Economics

- Subcontractors are paid from the project budget to set-up the IWW chain. However, since operations never can be subsidised in the EU legal environment, especially the economics of the transport should be in the focus, so that the transport can continue after the project's end in a competitive manner.
- However, the set-up of new supply chains with the help of the project financial means may be the necessary push towards regular IWT traffic there.

Legal framework

- Technologies which will operate constantly in the water like the Smart Buoys must meet the environmental requirements.

6. Key Performance Indicators

6.1. Introduction

This section outlines the specific metrics that will be used to measure the success of the pilots. It includes both quantitative and qualitative metrics and is aligned with the goals and objectives of the roadmaps.

The work regarding KPI has been carried out firstly in Del 1.1 and has been carried on in task 1.2. Together with WP6 as the interface to the pilot sites, that list was presented to the pilot sites to choose the most suitable ones.

The goal within Task 1.2 was to carry out business process mapping and define the main business processes and activities within the three pilots, with the main aim of increasing utilization of inland navigation infrastructure. Until month six the main efforts were concentrated on the Value Creation Circle (Fig.1.2.2.) of CRISTAL partners related to the general goals (the detailed business process plans are not fully available at the current state of the research).

The Value Creation Circle (VCC) represents the main R&D activities (WP2, WP3 and WP5) and their targeted results along the different system conditions (Normal operation, Deterioration, Limited operation and Recovery). Via the VCC, some KPIs can be derived (as metrics of the expected results for more accurate condition monitoring and forecasting capabilities, reduced uncertainty and advanced support for operative, tactical and strategic decisions) for the Pilot Sites and further possibilities open to analyse related to business processes (later in WP4, WP6, etc.).

Figure 5: Representation of the Value Creation Circle in the CRISTAL Project (authors' edition)

The main objective of the CRISTAL project is to increase the share of freight transport by inland waterway (IWT) by at least 20% and to demonstrate in its three pilot sites (Italy, Poland and France) strategies to improve reliability by 80%.

The CRISTAL project will ensure 50% of inland waterway capacity even during extreme weather events. To achieve this, CRISTAL will co-design, test and implement integrated, collaborative and innovative solutions in the three pilot partner areas identified in Italy, France and Poland.

It is also crucial to formulate KPIs in such a way that they highlight the factors that could hinder business growth (process risk, severity, occurrence, detection possibilities).

6.2. Leading and lagging KPIs

To support the KPI formulation process, the concept of leading and lagging KPIs was applied. Three levels of project KPIs have been identified, namely

- 1) KPIs for the overall project that are expected to be met according to the DoW;
- 2) KPIs within the pilots' operations and processes,
- 3) KPIs within a specific technologies: FOS, IBS, SIR, AE.

These three can further be summarized to two groups:

- Lagging: (overarching) project KPIs (top-down)
- Leading: KPIs related to pilots (bottom-up), so that both process related KPIs and technology assessment related KPI fall into that group.

6.3. Lagging, overarching respectively top-down KPI formulation

The Top-down KPI formulation strategy provides the lagging indicators, measuring the results achieved by the project completion.

Primary TD-Metrics (TD-M1)	derived from the project proposal,
Secondary TD-Metrics (TD-M2)	supported by the benchmarking of similar research and development projects (e.g., the NOVIMAR project).

The pitfall - related to lagging indicators - in the early stages of development is that some of the metrics seem far away (if at all) for pilot sites and teams.

The software technologies, the digital twin and the corridor management system support the extended technical and socio-economic environment to dynamically use the available resources and provide higher efficiency for more sustainable transport. Although the research and development activities and their implementation in the CRISTAL project will certainly contribute to increasing the attractiveness of inland waterway transport, the clear attribution of individual factors and their impact on the system as a whole remains a challenge.

H. Baroud et al. / Transportation Research Part E 62 (2014) 55–67

Figure 6: Relations of Projects Scopes and System Conditions (edition by KTI applying the chart of Baroud et. al.)

6.4. Leading respectively bottom-up KPI formulation

The bottom up KPI formulation strategy provides the leading indicators to support the R&D activities in the pilot sites.

The CRISTAL technologies that will provide information to the DT include

- Innovative distributed Fibre Optic Sensing (FOS) technology functionalised with weighing pads (laboratory only, no waterway installation considered in the project);
- Intelligent buoy system for measuring water levels in controlled waterways (with additional functions such as counting passing vessels, etc.);
- Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) technology; sensors to support health monitoring and preventive resilient management of IWW engineered structures (to identify maintenance issues with IWW features for planned maintenance).
- Acoustic Emission (AE) technology

Several technical and operational (process oriented) KPIs can be formulated based on the activities in each pilot, such as

- Number of intelligent sensors installed (pcs), working properly (%), critical river sections monitored by additional advanced sensors (pcs, km), waterway and infrastructure monitoring integrated in CRISTAL DSS, contributing to monitoring with additional information, etc. (in WP2)
- Number of inspections provided to detect cracks, discontinuities, their progress and trends, actions taken based on the results, actions planned and provided, etc. (in WP5)
- Number of additional partners invited and integrated into the synchromodal data community, number of shipments redirected, etc. (in WP3).
- emissions and costs saved by better management of vessel scheduling in ports, locks and other facilities (reduced emissions due to reduced speed and waiting time, impact of iron quays, etc.).

To achieve the SMARTTEST (significant, measurable, achievable, relevant, trackable, ethical, supported, time-bound) leading indicators for the initial phase, we propose a 4-step approach:

1. a detailed analysis of all responses to Questionnaire I (presented in D1.1) in relation to existing and desired data management requirements.
2. conduct a short survey with the members of the pilot R&D team based on the results of step 1 and benchmarking from the BU-M1 and BU-M2 literature.
3. identify the leading KPIs in an online workshop (FR, IT, PL).
4. summarise the results and get buy-in from the pilot R&D teams (they see the leading KPIs as SMARTTEST and linked to strategic imperatives, and they are able to track how performance changes).

The KPI system of D1.1 includes all these indicators and some additional ones related to the specific objectives and needs of the CRISTAL project. In the following table also individually formulated requests of the pilots regarding the KPIs are included. The process of choosing the KPIs per pilot is still not fully finalised while this deliverable has been compiled.

Table 7: Proposed Leading KPIs , Work in Progress End of May 2023

Proposed Leading KPIs
Efficiency
E1-Capacity levels during extreme weather events
E2-Early warning systems for extreme weather (extreme weather incidents detected / month)
E3-Capacity levels during
E4-Real-time infrastructure and water level monitoring (% of network covered)
E5-Tracked vs total shipments (% /month)
E6-Operational efficiency (tonnes/km)
E7-Status updates (updates/hour)
E8-Actual vs planned shipments (% of on-time shipments)
E9-Delays/Waiting times (E9- actual-estimated time of arrival as absolute value per shipment)
E10-Technical readiness level of technologies
E11-Resource availability / Asset management (% of assets digitalised/connected)
E12-Operational cost of a fixed route (E12- euro/cargo unit/km)
E13-Overall corridor transit time (minutes/km)
Environmental
ENV1-Share of freight transport on IWT
ENV2-Recycled materials
ENV3-Evaluation of material composition applied by IWT infrastructure
ENV4-NOX (g/kWh or %m/m)
ENV5-PM (µg/m ³)
ENV6-GHG as CO ₂ e (tonnes of CO ₂ e / tkm)
ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometre
Safety and social
S1-Number of new or adjusted governance models and solutions, roadmaps and guidelines
S2-Accidents along the transport network
S3-Time to react (response time/return time)
S4-Availability of multimodal transport information (Information publicly available - Likert scale)
S5-Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)
Polish pilot
UG-1 Tons Freight / TEU Freight
UG-2 Barge cargo capacity utilisation
UG-3 IWW share in total supply chain distance [km]
UG-4 Total manhours of people involed in supply chain
Italian Pilot

ITA-1 Users Reservation of Navigation Lock by Multimodal Platform
ITA-2 Navigation Bulletin downloads
ITA-3 Registered users
ITA-4 Navigation forecast points along the river

6.5. Inspiration taken from the NOVIMOVE Project

The evaluation framework of the NOVIMOVE project³ provides a systematic view of the overall impact of the project, and the different work packages reflect only the arms of the KPI spider that are relevant to the activities carried out by the pilots.

Figure 7: NOVIMOVE Novel inland waterway transport concepts for moving freight effectively (D 2.1.)

To be able to select the suitable KPIs from the list of different indicators a benchmarking action was carried out (although the goals of the NOVIMOVE and the CRISTAL Projects aim at different areas of IWT development).

6.6. Conclusion of the KPI selection

The above summarised input from pilot and other research projects has been the basis for a preselection of suitable key performance indicators for the three pilot sites and their associated living labs. Based on these suggestions and inspiration a list was formulated from which the pilot site owners can select in a

³ Novimove Project, <https://novimove.eu>

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joint effort with the work package 6 the most suited KPIs. Since the pilot sites are very different from each other, the pilot sites were given the opportunity to choose different KPIs according to their individual requirements.

While this deliverable was compiled, the selection of the final KPIs by the pilot sites owners has not been finalised yet. However, these are the choices in the work in progress.

Table 8: French pilot KPIs

Proposed KPIs	This KPI will be measured by- test or simulation	Measuring data
E1-Capacity levels during extreme weather events	test	- Develop the wide-gauge network, particularly within the framework of the Seine-Escaut network: compliance with the program validated and financed by Europe - Reliability of structures: number of breakdowns/structures/year
E2-Early warning systems for extreme weather (extreme weather incidents detected / month)	test	Progress rate of the modernization of the Hydraulic Management of the network
E3-Capacity levels during disruptions	test	- Availability rate (in %) on the wide gauge - Identify and assess the impacts of climate change on the network
E4-Real-time infrastructure and water level monitoring (% of network covered)	test	Functional state indicator of the structures
E5-Tracked vs total shipments (% /month)	test	Provision of RIS data on each basin of the wide-gauge network in the European EURIS portal
E8-Actual vs planned shipments (% of on-time shipments)	test	Provision of RIS data on each basin of the wide-gauge network in the European EURIS portal
E11-Resource availability / Asset management (% of assets digitalised/connected)	test	Integrated river-rail scheme for combined transport including the operating mode for "transfer" of flow between river and rail in the event of a service continuity problem (flood, damage, structure, line interruption): drawing up of a map on the Ile-de-France basin
E12-Operational cost of a fixed route (E12-euro/cargo unit/km)	test	Provision of RIS data on each basin of the wide-gauge network in the European EURIS portal
E13-Overall corridor transit time (minutes/km)	test	Provision of RIS data on each basin of the wide-gauge network in the European EURIS portal

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ENV1-Share of freight transport on IWT	test	Additional tonne-kilometres (Tk) generated by the Modal Shift Assistance Plan
ENV2-Recycled materials	test	% of non-hazardous sediment recovered
ENV3-Evaluation of material composition applied by IWT infrastructure	test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Progress rate of the works compliance program to strengthen ecological continuity - Number of works contracts including a provision in favor of sobriété énergétique
ENV4-NOX (g/kWh or %m/m)	test	Reduction rate of atmospheric pollutant emissions on engines supported by VNF: Nox
ENV5-PM ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	test	Rate of reduction of atmospheric pollutant emissions on engines supported by VNF: PM
ENV6-GHG as CO ₂ e (tonnes of CO ₂ e / tkm)	test	Reduction rate of atmospheric pollutant emissions on engines supported by VNF: CO ₂
ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometre (toe /tkm)	test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop the wide-gauge network, particularly within the framework of the Seine-Escaut network: compliance with the program validated and financed by Europe - Reliability of structures: number of breakdowns/structures/year
S1-Number of new or adjusted governance models and solutions, roadmaps and guidelines	test	Progress rate of the modernization of the Hydraulic Management of the network
S4-Availability of multimodal transport information (Information publicly available - Likert scale)	test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability rate (in %) on the wide gauge - Identify and assess the impacts of climate change on the network
S5-Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)	test	Functional state indicator of the structures

Table 9: Italian pilot KPIs

Proposed KPIs	This KPI will be measured by-test or simulation	What technology is this KPI related to	Measuring data
ENV4-NOX (g/kWh or %m/m)	estimate	cold ironing	<p>The feasibility study is evaluating the potential impact of cold ironing implementation.</p> <p>Data referred to: - Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco</p> <p>A possible generalization to the whole IWW could be implemented through the Living Lab</p>
ENV5-PM (µg/m ³)	estimate	cold ironing	<p>The feasibility study is evaluating the potential impact of cold ironing implementation.</p> <p>Data referred to: - Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco</p> <p>A possible generalization to the whole IWW could be implemented through the Living Lab</p>
ENV6-GHG as CO ₂ e (tonnes of CO ₂ e / tkm)	estimate	cold ironing	<p>The feasibility study is evaluating the potential impact of cold ironing implementation.</p> <p>Data referred to: - Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco</p> <p>A possible generalization to the whole IWW could be implemented through the Living Lab</p>
ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometre (toe /tkm)	estimate	cold ironing	<p>The feasibility study is evaluating the potential impact of cold ironing implementation.</p> <p>Data referred to: - Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco</p> <p>A possible generalization to the whole IWW could be implemented through the Living Lab</p>

S1-Number of new or adjusted governance models and solutions, roadmaps and guidelines	estimate	- cold ironing - Forecast model (output: smart bulletin)	Through the Living Lab, new governance models will be evaluated. For the cold ironing, the feasibility study will develop the implementation plan.
S5-Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)	test	Forecast model (output: smart bulletin)	Questionary/Tests with the involvement of the Living Lab
ITA 1_Users Reservation of Navigation Lock by Multimodal Platform	test	Multimodal platform (DT Smart Monitor)	Number of reservations
ITA2 Navigation Bulletin downloads	test	Multimodal platform (DT Smart Monitor)	Counter on the web site/service
ITA 3 Registered users	test	Multimodal platform (DT Smart Monitor)	Number of subscriptions
ITA 4_Navigation forecast points along the river	test	Forecast model (output: smart bulletin)	Number of forecast points

Table 10: Polish pilot KPIs

Proposed KPIs	My understanding of this KPI/my definition (optional)	This KPI will be measured by- test or simulation	What technology is this KPI related to	Measuring data
E5-Tracked vs total shipments (% /month)	% of shipments in measured supply chain chosen for pilot covered by GPS real time tracking devices	test	GPS on barge board / trucks	Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
E6-Operational efficiency (tonnes/km)	Total Tonnekm or TEUkm for containerised cargo transported during the pilot	test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
E7-Status updates (updates/hour)	A number of shipment status (ETA update) sent to forwarder/customer during the pilot	test	intelligent buoys	Arrival time (ETA for the shipments)
E8-Actual vs planned shipments (% of on-time shipments)		test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
E9- Delays/Waiting times (E9- actual-estimated time of arrival as absolute value per shipment)	% of shipments on time - verification - delivery notification time vs real delivery	test	intelligent buoys	ETA Time based on intelligent boys vs ATA provided by freight forwarder
E12- Operational cost of a fixed route (E12- euro/cargo unit/km)	providing final financial report on the total cost of supply chain / per tonne / per TEU	test		Cost assessment provided by freight forwarder - pilot performer
E13-Overall corridor transit time (minutes/km)	Measuring TT between cargo loading and cargo delivery	test	intelligent buoys	ETA Time based on intelligent boys vs ATA provided by freight forwarder
ENV1-Share of freight	Measuring cargo freighted by ITW (multimodal) in total	test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not

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transport on IWT	freight (per supply chain)			possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
ENV4-NOX (g/kWh or %m/m)	Measuring real emission during the voyage	test		IWW Operator/freight forwarder report
ENV5-PM ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Measuring real emission during the voyage	test		IWW Operator/freight forwarder report
ENV6-GHG as CO ₂ e (tonnes of CO ₂ e / tkm)	Measuring real emission during the voyage	test		IWW Operator/freight forwarder report
ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometre (toe /tkm)	Measuring real emission during the voyage	test		IWW Operator/freight forwarder report
S2-Accidents along the transport network				Only historical data, not directly referred to the pilots
S3-Time to react (response time/return time)				Based on Wody Polskie declaration
S4-Availability of multimodal transport information (Information publicly available - Likert scale)				As element of social survey, not directly referred to the pilot
S5-Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)				As element of social survey, not directly referred to the pilot
UG-1 Tons Freight / TEU Freight		test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
UG-2 Barge cargo capacity utilisation		test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution

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UG-3 IWW share in total supply chain distance [km]		test	Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
UG4 - Total manhours of people involved in supply chain		test	Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution

7. Conclusion

This section summarizes the key findings and recommendations of the report and provides an overall assessment of the feasibility and effectiveness of the roadmaps.

The three presented roadmaps are based on what is planned and will be carried out in the three pilot sites. To merge the different roadmaps into one concluding plan how to implement new technologies or new processes into the IWT sector is not considered as target oriented.

The overall objectives of the CRISTAL project are of holistic nature. They favour the system inland waterway transport rather than single goals or measures. The measures in the pilot sites have been selected because of the regional requirements that can be very different between IWT infrastructure sites in the European Union. If transferability of the project achievements is the aim, then these specific measures are more an example of how it can be done than a general blueprint.

A goal is understood as an achievable outcome that is generally broad and long-term while an objective defines measurable actions to achieve the overall goal. While goals are important for providing direction and motivation, they can also be limiting and create a narrow focus on the desired outcome, often neglecting the importance of the process or system that will enable the achievement of the goal.

To strengthen the overall IWT system, the pilot sites contribute with specific measures tested in laboratory conditions or in a real operational environment. By prioritizing the development of effective systems, the focus is the continuous improvement and refinement of the processes that support the attainment of the desired outcome. This approach emphasizes the importance of consistently and intentionally investing in systems that foster success and sustainable growth.

For example, rather than setting a goal of just measuring sedimentation in rivers, a "systems over goals" approach focuses on developing routines and processes around that data that will lead to a better navigation forecast almost as a by-product of the improved systems. The focus of CRISTAL is on creating a sustainable inland waterway transport system rather than just achieving single short-term goals.

The roadmaps illustrate in a great variety which strategies and tactics are applied to overcome the identified shortcomings in the overall IWT ecosystem. In CRISTAL, the system IWT ecosystem receives an input

- for an improvement for the infrastructure owners/ authorities
 - Better maintenance routines and more insights into the status of concrete walls and lock gates
 - Locating abandoned buoys
 - Feasibility of cold ironing facilities
- for the (potential users) of the IWT infrastructure
 - Electronic handling of freight documents

- Improved insights re. free berth facilities in ports and at locks
- More reliable and more detailed navigation forecasts
- New IWT supply chain models

However, in research projects, also pilot sites which may end in proving that certain technologies or measures are not or only partly suitable to achieve certain goals contribute to the state of the art in research. If that may occur, is not to be said at this early stage of the project.

The KPIs have been developed and selected to be able to validate the performance and results of the pilot within task 10.3 at a later stage. The project decided to provide a list to the pilots from which the chose the most suitable ones. It was also possible to add individual KPIs for the pilots. These KPIs will show if and how the planned enhancements in the IWT sector will have succeeded.

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